

Regional application of complex groundwater quality indices and mapping for the territory of Bulgaria with possibilities for their use

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Abstract. The aim of this study is to perform a spatial complex hydrochemical analysis of groundwater quality in Bulgaria and compile a map. For this purpose, data for the chemical composition (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , HCO_3^- , TDS, EC) of fresh groundwater (having shallow circulation) for the year 2015 have been summarized. These are the waters most vulnerable to incoming contaminants infiltrating from the surface and, at the same time, these are the waters of importance for the provision of potable water supply. The Groundwater Quality Index has been used to assess the water quality for domestic usage. An assessment of the potential groundwater's corrosive activity has also been made. For this purpose, the Langelier Saturation Index and the Potential to Promote Galvanic Corrosion were determined as well. The galvanic corrosion of water in respect to lead (expressed as the chloride-sulphate mass ratio) has not been determined and mapped on the territory of Bulgaria, nor has the Langelier index for fresh groundwater. For the year of 2015, the groundwater of the territory was classified as being in acceptable (76 to 90), and good (90 to 95) condition in terms of the Groundwater Quality Index. In terms of the Langelier Saturation Index and the Potential for Galvanic Corrosion, the territory of the country can be characterized by low to moderate potential (for galvanic corrosion), and according to LSI it can be classified in three categories – potentially corrosive, indeterminate, and scale forming.

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INTRODUCTION

Water is an essential component of the environment and an important factor for the existence of life on Earth. Its spatial position, forms of existence, and quantitative and qualitative properties are characterized by interdependencies and great dynamics in time and space. The groundwater in Bulgaria (located in the eastern part of the Balkan Peninsula, SE Europe) has a ubiquitous distribution, unevenly spread out in the course of time, and all over the territory of the country (Antonov and Danchev, 1980).

This requires its efficient use in different aspects of the social and economic life with minimal impacts on its quality. This fact, along with the varied physico-geographical and geological settings of the country, and many anthropogenic influences, determine certain spatial differences in the quality of groundwater. Numerous studies have been conducted in Bulgaria to characterize the chemical composition and establish the processes and extent of contamination for individual sites and regions. There are a few generalizations available for the entire country (Danchev, 1968; Kehajov, 1982, 1984,

Kehajov *et al.*, 2002; Benderev *et al.*, 2019; Gerginov *et al.*, 2019). Distributions of specific components in the country were given by Stanchev (1961, 1962) for the content of some alkaline and trace elements; by Kehajov (1968, 1978), for the total hardness and chlorides. Most of these studies were carried out in the second half of the 20th century. They provide insight into groundwater chemistry for that period. Spatial distribution of groundwater quality on the territory of Bulgaria by integral quality assessment was given by Vasileva (2020a). The data used to determine the Water Quality Index (WQI) are from Kehajov (1968). Trayanova *et al.* (2017, 2018, 2019) used the Langelier Saturation Index (LSI) to assess the probability of corrosion of borehole columns dripping thermal water. No regional assessments of the corrosion of groundwater used for drinking and industrial water supply have been made to date.

The aim of this paper is to analyze and establish the current state of the groundwater on the territory of Bulgaria and its suitability for various purposes – domestic and industrial. Characterization of the chemical composition and integral assessment of the groundwater's condition in terms of the content of the main physico-chemical components, affecting its quality, and listed in Annex 1 of the Regulation No.1 on the exploration, protection, and use of groundwater, was performed. Different approaches have been developed for quality assessment and zonation of groundwater (Venkata Mohan *et al.*, 1996; Backman *et al.*, 1998; Edet and Offiong, 2002; Babiker *et al.*, 2007; Kouli *et al.*, 2011; Dokou *et al.*, 2015; Balakrishnan and Ramu, 2016; Sobhanardakani *et al.*, 2017). A brief review of the methods used for assessing groundwater contamination was given by Panayotova *et al.* (2019). Some of these methods have been applied to assess groundwater quality in Bulgaria (Vasileva, 2020a–c).

In the present study, a method proposed by Babiker *et al.* (2007) and Mohebbi Tafreshi and Mohebbi Tafreshi (2017) was used. This is a comprehensive method for assessing the quality of groundwater for domestic purposes. The end result of its application was the compilation of a map showing groundwater quality (hydro-chemical state of

groundwater) by means of determining GQI for domestic purposes where a score ranking was used. In addition to potable usage, an assessment of the suitability of the water for industrial uses was also carried out. For this purpose, LSI and the Potential to Promote Galvanic Corrosion (PPGC) were determined. In the process of galvanic corrosion, metals degrade faster and lose their mechanical resistance. This, in turn, leads to corrosion of metallic equipment as well. Until now, the effects of galvanic corrosion of groundwater regarding lead, expressed as chloride-sulphate mass ratio (CSMR), has not been determined, and neither has the Langelier Index regarding fresh groundwater on the territory of Bulgaria. In conclusion, the aim of the assessment is to compile maps of the quality of groundwater on the territory of Bulgaria. The final result for GQI, LSI and PPGC is converted to a hexagonal grid where data from interpolation techniques have been preserved as much as possible.

DATA COLLECTION AND METHOD

Data processing and pre-processing

The countrywide assessment of untreated groundwater quality (water in its natural state) was based on the results from 1,300 samples analyzed in the 2015 monitoring by the Executive Environment Agency (ExEA). The data is from the control and operational monitoring networks, providing information on the chemical status of groundwaters found on the territories of the four basin districts – Danube River Basin Directorate, Black Sea River Basin Directorate, East Aegean River Basin Directorate, and West Aegean River Basin Directorate. The obtained point data was divided by seasons, and then raster maps were compiled for individual indicators (electrical conductivity, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, HCO₃⁻, TDS, pH) relevant to the groundwater quality indices used in this study. The annual raster maps (Fig. 1) used in the calculations was generated from the seasonal maps of the individual indices. The annual raster maps, which serve as the basis for the index calculations of GQI, LSI and CSMR, were generated from the seasonal maps

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Fig. 1. Annual distribution of chemical elements on the territory of Bulgaria in 2015: a) calcium in mg/L; b) chloride in mg/L; c) magnesium in mg/L; d) sodium in mg/L; e) sulfate in mg/L; f) nitrate in mg/L; g) electrical conductivity (EC) in µS/cm; h) bicarbonate in mg/L; i) total dissolved solid (TDS) in mg/L; j) pH-indicator (hydrogen indicator).

of the individual indices. The approach used for the creation of those seasonal maps in order to generate the annual map for the studied parameter was made necessary due to the incomplete and sporadic sampling of the monitoring network sites.

Groundwater quality was assessed by GQI, LSI and PPGC by individual zones. The individual regions have been separated according to Kehajov (1967). Kehajov (1967) divided the territory of the country into eight landscape-hydrochemical regions (Thrace, Moesia, Varna–Luda Kamchiya, Dobrudzha, Sofia, Burgas–Strandzha, Kraishte–Pirin, and Rila–Rhodopes). The division was made by taking into account the lithological, hydrodynamic, hydrochemical, and climatic conditions. For the present analysis, the individual zones have been digitalized, and their boundaries have been further refined according to the digital elevation model, DEM 90 m (Robinson *et al.*, 2014). During the digitalization process, the contours of the regions were presented in such a way as to follow the lines of the watershed ridges. In this way, the areas where groundwater formation and drainage occur have been shaped on the map.

Groundwater Quality Index

A complex parametric approach is applied. Parametric approaches are based on the combination of selected indicators affecting groundwater quality. Each indicator is assessed in relation to its importance to the overall quality assessment with a pre-defined value coefficient. A weighting factor for each indicator is also set. The quality assessment is obtained by summing the products of the value coefficient and the weighting factor for each indicator involved in the assessment. The final result is represented by a number giving an integral assessment of groundwater quality based on the components electrical conductivity (EC), Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , used in this particular case. A number of assessment approaches have been proposed under this methodology, according to the indicators used (Brown *et al.*, 1972; Babiker *et al.*, 2007; Chatterjee and Raziuddin, 2007; Jareda *et al.*, 2016; Singh and Hussian, 2016; Mohebbi Tafreshi and Mohebbi Tafreshi, 2017).

In the present work, the method described by Babiker *et al.* (2007) and Mohebbi Tafreshi and Mohebbi Tafreshi (2017) was used, which essentially gives an integral estimate of the groundwater chemical status. This is a variant of the complex approach where water quality is determined based on several indicators and the final result obtained is in

the form of a score, rank, or grade. The advantage is to obtain an overall final assessment of groundwater status. The essence of this method consists in the sequential execution of three steps: (i) in the first step, a map of the normalized values for each parameter involved in the assessment (or so-called normalized parametric map) is drawn as a ratio between the concentration of the parameter set in the standard (X) and the value of the concentration of the same parameter obtained from the monitoring observation (X') according to Equation 1:

$$(1) C = \frac{X' - X}{X' + X}.$$

The values obtained are in the range between (-1) and (+1). As the value approaches (+1), the groundwater quality deteriorates; (ii) in the second step, a quality rank map is constructed for each parameter. This map is obtained from the normalized map by the following polynomial:

$$(2) r = 0.5 \times C^2 + 4.5 \times C + 5.$$

The values of each map pixel vary from 1 to 10. The unit indicates areas of groundwater of good quality by concentration of the corresponding indicator. When values approach 10, the aquifer water quality deteriorates. At the end, the weight (w_i) of each parameter involved in the assessment is estimated by finding the average value of the parameter from all pixels of the raster map; (iii) in the third step, for each pixel of the annual raster maps produced, GQI is calculated using Equation 3. According to it, the water is classified on a five-level scale in terms of its drinking quality, from very good quality to very poor quality (Table 1).

$$(3) GQI = 100 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i \times w_i}{n},$$

where: r_i – rank values; w_i – relative weight of indicators; n – number of indicators. The average de-

Table 1
Groundwater quality classification according to GQI

Quality	GQI Class*
Good	90–100
Acceptable	70–90
Medium	50–70
Poor	25–50
Unpleasant	0–25

Note: *After Mohebbi Tafreshi and Mohebbi Tafreshi (2017)

Table 2
Corrosion category according to LSI

Classification	LSI*
Potentially corrosive	< -0.5
Indeterminate	-0.5 to 0.5
Scale forming	> 0.5

Note: *After Belitz *et al.* (2016)

Table 3
Groundwater classification according to PPGC

Classification	CSMR*	Alkalinity, mg/L
Low	< 0.2	–
Moderate	0.2–0.5	–
Moderate	> 0.5	≥ 50
High	> 0.5	< 50

Note: *After Belitz *et al.* (2016)

terminated from the minimum and maximum values of the rank map is taken as the relative weight (Mohebbi Tafreshi and Mohebbi Tafreshi, 2017).

Langelier Saturation Index and Potential to Promote Galvanic Corrosion

The study also identifies the potential for corrosion of groundwater across the country. Two indicators were used to assess the potential corrosivity of the water, LSI (Langelier, 1936) and PPGC (Belitz *et al.*, 2016). The saturation index was determined by Equation 4:

$$(4) \text{ LSI} = \text{pH} - \text{pH}_s,$$

where pH is the measured value of the hydrogen index in water, and pH_s is the hydrogen index at calcite saturation (CaCO_3).

Groundwater PPGC was determined by CSMR or Equation 5:

$$(5) \text{ CSMR} = \text{Cl}^-/\text{SO}_4^{2-},$$

where the respective concentrations are expressed in mg/L.

In Belitz *et al.* (2016), groundwater is classified on a three-grade scale in terms of saturation index (potentially corrosive waters, undetermined, and waters forming limescale or calcite deposition). Based on CSMR and alkalinity (mg/L as CaCO_3), PPGC is graded as low, moderate, and high (Tables 2, 3).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main parameters used to determine GQI, LSI, PPGC, and their distributions over the country are presented in Fig. 1. GQI for the territory of Bulgaria was calculated with the help of Equation 3. The final raster was averaged as a median value and converted to a hexagonal grid. In this way, the spatial form of the applied data interpolation can be preserved as much as possible. Analysis of the results shows that groundwater, in terms of concentrations of selected chemical indicators, is primarily in acceptable status (GQI = 76–90), corresponding to 73% of the territory of Bulgaria, or good status (GQI = 90–95), corresponding to 27% of the territory of the country (Fig. 2).

LSI (Fig. 3) was used to produce a map of groundwater corrosive action showing the results obtained in the course of this study. In approximately 8.4% of the area of Bulgaria, the groundwater can be classified as potentially corrosive (LSI from -2.0 to -0.5), about 90.5% as indeterminate (LSI from -0.5 to 0.5), and only 1.1% (LSI from 0.5 to 2.0) as scale forming. A larger part of the country falls into the undefined category. In the indeterminate category are included groundwater areas that may also be considered marginally potentially corrosive in the range from -0.5 to 0.0, as well as regions (sites) that can be considered borderline scale forming – in the range between 0.0 and 0.5. That is because, according to Langelier (1936), negative values indicate that CaCO_3 deposition is unlikely and positive values indicate favorable terms for scale forming (CaCO_3 deposition). Roberge (2007) gave limiting values close to zero.

The groundwater PPGC for the country (Fig. 4) is estimated to be low (CSMR < 0.2) for about 6% of the country, and moderate ($0.2 \leq \text{CSMR} \leq 0.5$ and $\text{CSMR} > 0.5$; alkalinity ≥ 50) for about 93% of its territory. In only two areas in the country, a spring near Aleko Hut in the Vitosha Mountain and the spring 'Shalvarishte', Fotinovo Village, the groundwater is assessed with high (CSMR > 0.5 and alkalinity < 50; Figs 4, 5) potential to galvanic corrosion or nearly 0.4% of the territory of the country are evaluated with high potential for galvanic corrosion.

The territory of the country was divided into several zones, as specified by Kehayov (1967), for which an assessment of groundwater quality and corrosivity is given below (Table 4). In terms of GQI, the values are similar, being highest in the mountainous areas where water exchange occurs most rapidly. Highest alkalinity values are observed

Fig. 2. Spatial values of the GQI method in hexagonal grid (median values).

Fig. 3. Langelier Saturation Index (LSI) – spatial values for the territory of Bulgaria in hexagonal grid (median values).

Fig. 4. Potential to promote galvanic corrosion (PPGC) for the territory of Bulgaria in hexagonal grid (median values).

Fig. 5. Alkalinity as $CaCO_3$ for the territory of Bulgaria in hexagonal grid (median values).

Table 4
Characteristic mean values and classification of GQI, LSI, PPGC for the eight regions of Bulgaria

Region Name	Area, m ²	Classification				GQI	LSI	PPGC
		GQI	LSI	PPGC	Alkalinity, mg/L			
Moesia Region	3.33E+10	88	0.04	0.5	332	Good	Indeterminate	Moderate
Dobrudzha Region	1.07E+10	87	0.1	1.0	361	Good	Indeterminate	Moderate
Varna–Luda Kamchiya Region	8.96E+09	88	0.1	0.6	313	Good	Indeterminate	Moderate
Sofia Region	4.44E+09	89	−0.1	0.3	230	Good	Indeterminate	Moderate
Thrace Region	2.69E+10	88	−0.2	0.5	226	Good	Indeterminate	Moderate
Burgas–Strandzha Region	7.11E+09	87	0.1	0.8	348	Good	Indeterminate	Moderate
Kraishte–Pirin Region	8.99E+09	90	−0.04	0.3	231	Good	Indeterminate	Moderate
Rila–Rhodopes Region	1.05E+10	92	−0.2	0.6	189	Good	Indeterminate	Moderate

in Dobrudzha region. In this zone, karst aquifers in carbonate rocks are more common. The lowest alkalinity values are in the Rila–Rhodopes region, where silicate rocks are widespread.

The lowest values for GQI were obtained in the Varna–Luda Kamchiya, Thrace, and Burgas–Strandzha regions (Fig. 6a). Additionally, in the Black Sea area, the lower GQI score is most likely due to seawater intrusion. In the south of Bulgaria, the lower values are in the regions of KCM 2000–Plovdiv, Haskovo field, Maritsa-East area, and the Black Sea mines (near Burgas). These are areas with a distribution of volcanic-sedimentary rocks and fluvial materials; areas with alternating sandy and clayey Neogene deposits and within the tectonic graben-like depressions in southern Bulgaria. The lower values for GQI were obtained in northern Bul-

garia, in the platform cover where alternating sandy and clayey Neogene deposits north of the Balkan Mountain occur. For North Bulgaria, these values are probably due to the presence of higher concentrations of magnesium ions in the groundwater due to loess cover, the distribution of the Sarmatian and Upper Jurassic–Valanginian aquifers, which have a more delayed water exchange. In the northwest of Bulgaria, the lower values are probably due to the waters of the Timok River and intensive agriculture in the region. In the Sofia Basin, due to anthropogenic load, lower values for GQI are also found. In SW Bulgaria, in the Petrich area, the lower GQI values found are due to increased agriculture, *i.e.*, the lower values for GQI are due to the areas with anthropogenic load combined with delayed groundwater exchange.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 6. Characteristic values (min, max, mean) of the: a) Groundwater Quality Index; b) Langelier Saturation Index; c) Chloride–Sulphate mass ratio; d) Alkalinity (mg/L as CaCO₃) for the eight regions of Bulgaria.

The obtained results show that the water-hosting medium plays an important role for the LSI results. In the platform environment in northern Bulgaria, LSI values are lower. This is quite normal, since there is a proliferation of resistant aquifers, and therefore the water exchange is more delayed. When combining mountain massifs with cracked and karst waters and tectonic grabens filled with Neogene deposits, the widest range of changes in LSI values is obtained (Fig. 6b). In the mountainous areas, the total dissolved solid of groundwater is low. Predisposed to scale forming are groundwaters formed in: Quaternary and Neogene clays; Mesozoic marls in North Bulgaria; Lower Paleozoic phyllites and shales in the Western Balkan Mountains; some areas in southeastern Bulgaria, with a distribution of volcanic-sedimentary rocks and fluvial materials; alternating sandy and clayey Neogene deposits north of the Balkan Mountains and filling tectonic graben-like depressions in South Bulgaria. In the area north of Sofia City, as well as in the area of the town of Varna (Neogene sands with clay and sandstone interbeds) and north of Burgas (Paleogene marls, clays, sands, and limestones), groundwater is most prone to scale forming.

Where there is delayed water exchange, *i.e.*, slower movement of groundwater, there are processes of dissolution of the host environment (dissolution of rocks) and, where volcanogenic-sedimentary complexes are distributed in the region of Burgas, there are high concentrations of chlorine and sulfate ions, and therefore the CSMR ratio is higher (Fig. 6c). In mountainous areas, the CSMR ratio changes to a lesser degree, *i.e.*, where there is a more intensive exchange of groundwater (faster water renewal).

With regard to alkalinity, local zones with higher values have been established (Fig. 6d). These are areas with more delayed water exchange, as well as the Black Sea coal mines in the region of Burgas.

CONCLUSION

The results give a snapshot of Bulgarian groundwater hydrochemistry in 2015. The reason this particular year was chosen is because of the fact that the

monitoring observations and data collection are the most complete. Several maps have been compiled using GIS methods to provide a spatial assessment of groundwater quality in Bulgaria. At its core, the Groundwater Quality Index is a method for cumulative assessment of groundwater quality for domestic purposes, showing its status in the form of a derived numerical expression. The final result obtained is in the form of a number and gives a certain status to the groundwater and groups it into predefined quality classes. The benefit of its application is the possibility to define groundwater quality zones and analyze the suitability of the water for different purposes. The GQI results obtained for 2015 classify the groundwater on the territory of Bulgaria in acceptable (GQI from 76 to 90) to good status (GQI from 90 to 95) for both drinking and domestic usage. In determining groundwater quality indices, a very important step is the determination of relative weight for each parameter in the overall quality assessment. The quality index equation used does not take into account disease-causing microorganisms, as well as the presence of heavy metals, such as copper, lead, arsenic, etc. In terms of the Langelier Saturation Index and Potential for Galvanic Corrosion, the country is characterized by low (PPGC from 0.0 to 0.2) to moderate potential for galvanic corrosion at alkalinity > 50 mg/L as CaCO₃, and falls into three categories related to LSI: potentially corrosive (LSI from -2.0 to -0.5), indeterminate (LSI from -0.5 to 0.5), and scale forming (LSI from 0.5 to 2.0).

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